

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Deliverables/Milestones

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Executive Summary

The milestone is from WP2: Consolidating the Training Platform Infrastructure (services and resources), Activity 1: Expanding the TMD to support communities and standards. The milestone is called M2.7 Version 2: Support the development of the TMD through the submission of BioHackathon proposals every year, and the goal is to submit a proposal to the Biohackathon 2025.

This project has been accepted in Biohackathon 2025 and will enhance the TMD by developing a new API and customizable widgets to improve usability, automation, and visibility across ELIXIR nodes and beyond. It aims to support better integration with ELIXIR systems, reduce manual data entry, and enable stakeholders to easily showcase training impact.

Early outcomes, aligned to the initial goals involve a TMD API endpoint being developed to enable read/write connections with other ELIXIR systems (e.g., TeSS) and node-specific platforms. Moreover customizable widgets have started to be developed on top of the API so nodes and ELIXIR centrally can display TMD data on their own websites. The overall goal is to make direct system-to-TMD integration feasible to automate data uploads, preserving the option for nodes to continue manual entry or adopt API-based flows. More information can be found in the TMD GitHub page <https://github.com/elixir-europe-training/Training-Metrics-Database> and the TMD wiki documentation here <https://github.com/elixir-europe-training/Training-Metrics-Database/wiki>.

Full proposal

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Opening the TMD: making it more Usable, Visible, and Connected

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Abstract

This project aims to extend the functionality of the Training Metrics Database (TMD) by introducing a new API endpoint and customizable widgets.

The Training Metrics Database (TMD) is an ELIXIR multi-node service that aggregates and measures the impact of training across the ELIXIR nodes. It is an important resource for nodes in collecting and summarizing training statistics from their respective nodes. As part of a longer term plan of updating and making the TMD more user friendly, as well as relevant to communities outside of ELIXIR, we propose the development of an API to enable interaction with the database. Adding an API to the system is important for laying the foundation for future integrations and collaborations, with the goal of fully integrating the TMD into the ELIXIR ecosystem. This will, for example, make it possible for nodes to build custom automatic uploads to the TMD, reducing manual work, or connecting several ELIXIR systems together with the TMD. On top of the API we will also build a customizable widget that nodes can use to display their training statistics on websites, thereby showing their impact.

We will assemble a cross-functional team of web developers and people involved in training and training impact, to ensure we deliver solutions tailored to the needs of the ELIXIR Training community.

Scope and Vision

The goals of this project are:

- Develop a TMD API endpoint that allows for connections to other ELIXIR systems, such as TeSS, or node specific systems, both for getting and adding data.
- Create customizable widgets on top of the API that can be used by nodes and ELIXIR centrally to display data from the TMD integrated into their own websites.

This will create value in several ways:

- By making it possible for the nodes to directly integrate their systems to the TMD, data upload will be more automated. One of the barriers for full usage of the TMD in ELIXIR is the time consumption of manually uploading data. By giving the option of using the API, nodes can themselves choose whether to keep uploading data manually or integrate it directly into their own systems
- Using widgets to display TMD on their websites allows nodes to easily share the impact of their training to their customers and stakeholders. Similarly, ELIXIR centrally can use it to display the overall impact and reach of all trainings from the nodes
- Creating an API also enhances the TMD's usage outside of ELIXIR, as it can more easily be integrated with all other systems that uses APIs

This work is part of a longer development plan for the TMD, creating a more flexible and user friendly system, and further integrating it into the ELIXIR ecosystem.

Alignment with ELIXIR 2024-26 Programme and beyond

This project aligns with the objectives under Work package 2 in the Training Platform programme, by enhancing the usability and interoperability of the TMD. The work programme focuses on adding functionalities to make the TMD more user friendly and support not only the ELIXIR nodes, but also communities outside of ELIXIR. This Biohackathon proposal is part of a longer term plan to develop the TMD to reach these goals.

The TMD, especially when used in combination with ELIXIR core metrics, offers a foundational resource for assessing training impact, something increasingly relevant to external stakeholders, funders, and other infrastructures.

These developments contribute to the long-term goal of making the TMD a flexible, integrated, and externally usable service.

Feasibility

The goal of the week is to achieve the 3 following tasks, working in 3 parallel working groups of around 2 persons, and publish a functional new release of the TMD:

- Backend: adding an API to the Django codebase
- Widget implementation: Create the javascript widget using specifications from the backend and UX/UI team
- UX/UI: Design of the widget appearance and what features it should have

Skills that are needed are:

- Python and Django API implementation
- Javascript
- Knowledge of TMD data and how nodes use it
- Design of user interfaces

As many of the participants are knowledgeable in Python and Django, many of them would have the competence needed for this project.

Inclusivity strategy

This project will be a hybrid project, with participants having the option to participate online during the week. The week will start with an introduction to the TMD for newcomers to the project, and an update of the work that has been done previously.

We will utilize GitHub for code collaboration and task management, with an open repository where it is clear how to contribute to the project. By dividing the work into three teams, we will have two teams that need some technical understanding, while one team focuses more on usability, making sure everyone can contribute regardless of background.

Link to proposal

<https://app.oxfordabstracts.com/stages/77739/submissions/1051284/form/view>

Outcomes and Impacts of the deliverable

This proposal is in line with the overall aim of expanding the TMD to make it more accessible to all the Nodes, and other stakeholders interested in using the TMD. It supports the continued evolution of the TMD into a more accessible and integrated service for ELIXIR Nodes by introducing an API and reusable widgets.